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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 6.6 – VALIDATION AND EVALUATION

(FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the fulfilment of functional, non-functional, technical and privacy requirements defined in the original project proposal and deliverables D2.1 “Use Case Specification (first version)” and D2.2 “Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version)”. Aiming towards the fulfilment of requirements when developing XR technologies in THEIA^{XR} ensured to recognize important components of effective solutions for machine operation and their consequences on work performance and human and system factors. The work has been done in close co-operation with work package WP3 – Transdisciplinary Co-Design, and work package WP4 – Cyber-Physical Human-Machine Interaction, where XR interaction sequences were compiled (see D3.2 “Interaction Scenarios (first version)”), XR interaction concept defined (see D4.4 “Interaction concepts (first version)”), privacy-related questions discussed (see D3.3 “Prototypes for privacy-related questions (first version)”), and prototypes developed (see D3.4 “Low-fidelity XR Prototypes (first version)”). Results also contributed to detail and further specify our use cases (see D2.4 “Use Case Specification (final version)”) and technology requirements (see D2.5 “Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (final version)”).

As discussed in detail in deliverable D 6.3 “Validation and evaluation (first version)”, THEIA^{XR} applied a variety of evaluation measures to ensure technology development meets these goals. Our validation and evaluation efforts cover (i) controlled lab-based experiments for evaluating of the developed technologies and methodologies of THEIA^{XR}, (ii) trials of the XR and human-machine interaction applications of the 3 use cases in relevant environment, and (iii) a cross checking to assess the generality of the THEIA^{XR} technologies and methodologies. Finally, with technology development and validation completed, this deliverable reports on the assessment of requirements fulfilment.

Out of these 230 items, **164** were fulfilled to 100%. **5** achieved high ratings between 100 and 80%. **31** achieved intermediate ratings between 80 and 20%, of which **19** concern requirements labeled as MUST. The remaining **30** items did not apply to the respective technology, use case, component, or procedure.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable reports on the fulfilment of functional, non-functional and use-case related requirements. Initial requirements were defined in the original project proposal and subsequently refined in deliverables D2.1 “Use Case Specification (first version)” and D2.2 “Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version)”, after functional prototypes allowed early insights into effective XR solution and their consequences on work performance and human and system factors. The work has been done in close co-operation with work package WP3 – Transdisciplinary Co-Design, and work package WP4 – Cyber-Physical Human-Machine Interaction, where XR interaction sequences were compiled (see D3.2 “Interaction Scenarios (first version)”), XR interaction concept defined (see D4.4 “Interaction concepts (first version)”), privacy-related questions discussed (see D3.3 “Prototypes for privacy-related questions (first version)”), and prototypes developed (see D3.4 “Low-fidelity XR Prototypes (first version)”). THEIA^{XR} applied a variety of evaluation measures to ensure technology development meets these goals. Our validation and evaluation efforts covered (i) controlled lab-based experiments, (ii) expert evaluations, and (iii) the assessment of the generality of the THEIA^{XR} technologies and methodologies. This deliverable is structured as follows: section 2 recalls the defined requirements and section 3 reports on the requirement fulfilment levels.

2 Defined Requirements for THEIA^{XR} Technologies

The original project proposal defined several general and use case-specific KPIs as listed in the following Tables 1,2,3, and 4.

#	General KPIs
1	Improve safety for operator, vehicle and nearby skiers or other civilians
2	Reassure good usability
3	Consider privacy relations
4	Improve quality of work

Table 1: General KPIs for XR technologies and their integration in user interfaces

These KPIs were elaborated in an initial requirement analysis phase, by identifying operation and performance issues. Tables 2, 3, and 4 summarize the findings of deliverables D2.1 and D2.2.

#	Issues in Use Case 1 – Snow grooming
1	No established visualization form for the required information.
2	Due to the limited view around the vehicle, it is hard to see/detect obstacles around.
3	Operator needs to work in complete “whiteout” with no view.
4	With no view, it is not possible to detect obstacles with the eyes.

Table 2: KPI-related issues in the snow grooming use case

#	Issues in Use Case 2 – Logistics
1	Impaired visibility to target position and container.
2	Impaired visibility to obstacles around the machine.
3	Difficulty to estimate distances between objects.
4	Trailer twist locks can get stuck.
5	Material damages happen due to operation mistakes.
6	Safety (persons around the machine and other vehicles) harm exists.
7	Productivity of the remote-controlled system is not competitive to cabin-based machine operation.
8	Latency and reliability of the communication is critical for accurate operation.

Table 3: KPI-related issues in the logistics use case

#	Issues in Use Case 3 - Construction
1	The operator's views on the attachment and the graphical user interface are not in one visual axis.
2	Current 3D machine control interfaces offer a visual display of target and actual bucket height. It hardly allows a comprehensive view of the entire work area to plan e.g., backfilling.
3	Current operation requires confident usage and understanding of 3D-machine control systems and confidence in proper alignment of 3D models to the real world.
4	Spatial imagination to align the abstract, virtual reference model with real references.
5	Infield design requires a spatial imagination to design profiles and outlines with reference to the real environment.
6	Collision Warning Systems often annoy the operator due to the high frequency of warnings. This leads to deactivation of these systems in state-of-the-art applications.

Table 4: KPI-related issues in the construction use case

The conducted requirement and tasks analysis activities identified **six main sets of functional requirements**:

1. **General Functional Requirements** define what a system must do, detailing specific features, behaviours, and functions, encompasses the technologies and methodologies generally developed in the project and are applicable beyond the scope of the three use cases.
2. **Use Case-Specific Functional Requirements** are specific to the technologies and use scenarios of each use case.
3. **General Non-Functional Requirements** define how a system should work and describe properties that the system functions must/should/may have. These typically include performance, scalability, usability, security and other qualitative requirements that may be defined or expressed in absolute or relative terms.
4. **Use Case Specific Non-Functional Requirements** are specific to the technologies and use scenarios of each use case again.
5. **Technical Requirements** cover functionalities, organization, and architecture issues as well as technology features that are internal to the functioning of the different XR-technologies to be developed. They define specific, measurable standards of our developed XR-

technologies, covering performance (speed, reliability), safety (encryption, access), compatibility, data handling, and underlying infrastructure.

6. **Privacy requirements** define how to implement our Privacy by Design approach by specifying how data protection must be embedded to meet legal mandates (like GDPR) and build user trust.

All requirements are identified by a unique Requirement ID, so they can be traced throughout the development of the technologies. Use case-specific functional requirements are also associated with at least one scenario. Each requirement is appointed by a Level, based on a MUST/SHOULD/MAY rating. Requirements marked as “MUST” are crucial and obligatory to be implemented. Those marked as “SHOULD” described functionalities that are considered welcome features, and the ones marked as “MAY” are optional ones.

The requirements of THEIA^{XR} are provided in the following Table 5.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if they are fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals).	MUST	Technology
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery.	SHOULD	Technology
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment to identify dangerous situations.	MUST	Technology
GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness.	MUST	Technology
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback).	MUST	Technology
GFR6	The operator support system should allow users to customise UI components.	SHOULD	UI Concept
GFR7	The operator must be able to overcome the guidance provided by the support system, as he/she is the ultimate decision-maker.	MUST	UI Concept
GFR8	A software development toolkit must be available for developing UIs and hosting XR applications on the visualization infrastructure and interaction systems.	SHOULD	UI Concept
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator’s perception.	MUST	Technology
Use Case-Specific Functional Requirements			

FR.UC1.001	XR HMI system must show the distance between actual and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC1.002	XR HMI system must show the distance between blade and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC1.003	XR HMI system must show the distance between tracks and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC1.004	XR HMI system should indicate the required action to minimize delta to target surface.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC1.005	XR HMI system should inform operator on fulfilment rate.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC1.006	XR HMI system must inform operator in case of obstacle or boundary proximity.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC1.007	The XR HMI system must inform operator in case of new static or dynamic obstacle information availability.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC1.008	The XR HMI system must inform operator about location and identification of obstacles.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC1.009	The XR HMI system must inform operator about proposed action to avoid collision with an obstacle.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC2.001	The teleoperation support system should show the operator the job order via AR/XR in video feed. E.g., also highlights container location.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC2.002	The teleoperation support system must show operator spreader corner in video overlay via AR/XR.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC2.003	The teleoperation support system should show operator distance between handled objects (e.g., spreader and container) in video overlay via AR/XR.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC2.004	The teleoperation support system must allow operators to choose XR supported 3D and/or bird view to lift/lay down containers without collision.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC2.005	The teleoperation support system should provide operator XR-supported safety warning, if someone (human or machine is arriving close to working area.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC2.006	The teleoperation support system must provide haptic feedback to the operator.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC2.007	The teleoperation support system must provide audio feedback to operators from distance and location before collision.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC3.001	The operator interface system must visualize a digital representation of the machine and a terrain model of the environment.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC3.002	The operator interface system must visualize the excavator bucket position in relation to the target design height at that particular position.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC3.004	The operator interface system must visualize the point cloud data from the LiDAR as a continuously updated map.	MUST	Use Case

FR.UC2.005	The operator interface system must inform the operator about persons in the slewing radius in an intuitive but unobtrusive way.	MUST	Use Case
FR.UC3.006	The operator interface system should augment video streams with digital design data.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC3.007	The operator interface system should visualize the overall working area and the delta between actual and target height across the whole map.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC3.008	The operator interface system should show the position of known underground media in an intuitive way.	SHOULD	Use Case
FR.UC3.009	The operator interface system should enable the operator to modify the digital design model within the augmented video feed.	SHOULD	Use Case
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine.	MUST	Technology
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
GNFR4	The design and development process must involve representative vehicle operators in all major design and evaluation activities and provide them with opportunities to influence design and development decisions for their respective use-case.	MUST	Dev Process
GNFR5	During the design and implementation of feature ideas and interaction concepts, the utility, usability, safety and positive user experience for the human operators should always be prioritized above conflicting interests, unless technical feasibility is not given, or privacy infringements are detected.	SHOULD	Dev Process
GNFR6	The implementation of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data.	SHOULD	Technology
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	Technology
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR	MUST	Technology

	technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it.		
GNFR10	At least one concept for positive user experience must be integrated and tested in one of the final demonstrators.	MUST	Dev Process
GNFR11	The design of the overall system architecture should have the potential to be extended to support new/additional sensors, XR technologies, or output devices.	SHOULD	UI Concept
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
GNFR13	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	SHOULD	UI Concept
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
GNFR15	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	UI Concept
GNFR16	Where UX-enhanced features are integrated into the system interface, there should be a clear method for users to opt in or opt out.	SHOULD	UI Concept
Use Case Specific Non-Functional Requirements			
UCNFR.1 (UC2)	When the human operator is controlling the reachstacker, the XR information and control commands should be received in real-time.	SHOULD	Use Case
UCNFR.2 (UC3)	The displayed information and visualization must represent the actual situation with a maximal latency of 1s or clearly indicate an insufficient visualization.	MUST	Use Case
UCNFR.3 (UC3)	Any sensor or system function which is not operable must be clearly shown on the UI so that the operator can assess the system's functionality.	MUST	Use Case
UCNFR.4 (UC3)	The system must be operable even if no sufficient GNSS signal is available.	MUST	Use Case
Technical Requirements			
TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. framerate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not	SHOULD	Technology

	higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.		
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
TR7	Physical means will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to mount external equipment (e.g., rooftop mount for projectors, active lights and cameras).	MUST	Use Case
TR8	Electrical powering facilities and wiring options will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to power external equipment (e.g., up to 220V power rails for active lights and projectors).	MUST	Use Case
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes).	SHOULD	Technology
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms (arm64) has to be present.	MUST	Technology
Privacy requirements			
PR1	The use cases shall identify which personal data they are processing.	MUST	Use Case
PR2	The use cases shall adopt a data minimization approach.	SHOULD	Use Case
PR3	When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it.	SHOULD	Use Case

PR4	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	SHOULD	Use Case
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
PR7	Where UX-enhanced features are integrated into the system interface, there should be a clear method for users to opt in or opt out.	SHOULD	UI Concept

Table 5: Complete list of defined requirements within THEIA^{XR}

3 Requirement fulfilment

The following sections list the fulfilment ratings for all general, use case-related, technical and privacy-related requirements. As they apply to either specific XR-technologies, use cases, the involved user interface or the development process, this section is structured along with them. The following technologies were developed in THEIA^{XR} and associated requirements were rated separately for them:

- Object Recognition with Light Feedback (see section 3.1)
- Virtual Pit geometry/tool guidance with Matrix Display and Light Feedback (see section 3.2)
- Calibrated environment projection (see section 3.3)
- LiDAR augmented 3D Data on GUI (see section 3.4)
- Remote Operation Terminal with augmented camera streams (see section 3.5)
- Haptic Feedback Joystick (see section 3.6)
- Thermal camera with object recognition (see section 3.7)

Fulfilment of each requirement is documented by fulfilment level (0 to 100%), justification statement, test method, and reference to the associated deliverable. Technology requirements that do not apply to the respective XR technology are marked as “does not apply”.

3.1 Object Recognition with Light Feedback

This XR technology consists of an object detection system that analyses video footage of an array of cameras that are mounted on the machine. It identifies if a person is in the covered area around the machine and provides real-time information about its position relative to the machine (orientation and distance). This information is then spatial mapped and displayed on an LED-strip that is permanently mounted on the operation environment (e.g. windscreen, terminal display, or monitor). The fulfillment of requirements that apply to this technology is stated in the table below.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	Technology
100%	This is done by a status LED.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	Technology
100%	It is integrated in the excavator.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is active during operation.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	Technology
90%	The light feedback system extends the situational awareness, although it is not based on an HMD.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Technology
50%	The visual light feedback system is only one component of the operator support system.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception.	MUST	Technology
100%	It is not blocking the view and will only light up if there is a potential risk.	User evaluation	D6.1
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is active during operation.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology
100%	The latency of the system is approx. 150ms for the 100-100Base-T1-cameras.	Functional Testing	D6.1

GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The system runs on a dedicated CAN-Bus and is integrated into the electronic system.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it	MUST	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system increases safety while improving usability compared to state-of-the-art camera monitor systems.	User Evaluation	D3.10
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology

80%	The object detection system is trained to detect persons (vs. non-human objects) on construction site but is not yet fully validated for fairness because this is out of scope of the project.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
Technical Requirements			
TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. framerate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic interface in light feedback module		
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic interface in light feedback module		
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system runs on 24VDC.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
0%	The system is developed in Python.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The system has a CAN interface for the LED-control and an Ethernet interface for the cameras.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The System has a CAN interface for the LED-control and an Ethernet interface for the cameras.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be	SHOULD	Technology

	developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)		
100%	A free construction machine specific data set for person detection training has been used (https://zenodo.org/records/14884208)	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms (arm64) must be present.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: For the light feedback system, no unity license is necessary.		
Privacy requirements			
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
66%	The object detection system is trained to detect persons on construction site and tested on different individuals. However, we did not test it specifically on dark skinned individuals. For future development of the technology, we decided to opt-out for thermal cameras instead of general cameras, the consideration for fairness becoming fulfilled, as the temperature of the object is independent for the human-related fairness parameters (e.g. skin colour).	Technology Assessment	D6.5
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing about the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
100%	There is a sticker that informs about person detection.	Functional Testing	D6.5

Table 6: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the object recognition with light feedback system

3.2 Virtual Pit geometry/tool guidance with Matrix Display and Light Feedback

This XR technology consists of a virtual model of the machine based on real time data of implemented sensors that measure positions of machine components and the machine as a whole relative to the environment. It also uses 3D models that define reference geometries of the production task (e.g., target slope surface (UC1 – snow grooming), container locations (UC2 - logistics), and target pit surface (UC3 - construction). This data is used to calculate spatial deviations between tool or machine positions that are then displayed as visual indicators on a LED matrix display or light-strip. The fulfillment of requirements that apply to this technology are stated in the table below.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	Technology
100%	If a visual indicator is visible, it is working as expected.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	Technology
100%	It is integrated into the excavator.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is active during operation.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	Technology
90%	The height indicator is directly in the field of view.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Technology
50%	The visual indication is only one component of the operator support system. Other sub-systems support haptic feedback (snow groomer controls).	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception.	MUST	Technology
100%	It is not blocking the view and can be switched off, if not used.	User Evaluation	D3.10
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is active during operation.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology

100%	The system shows the vicinity of potential collision objects (e.g., underground media) within 200ms	Functional Testing	D6.1
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The system runs on a dedicated CAN-Bus and is integrated into the electronic system.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it	MUST	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system increases performance by improving the usability of the 3D machine control system.	User Evaluation	D6.1

GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No object detection is used.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
Technical Requirements			
TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. framerate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptics in UC3		
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptics in UC3		
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system runs on 24VDC	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The application is implemented in C and C#.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The LED-driver and the sensors are connected via CAN-bus.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The LED-driver and the sensors are connected via CAN-bus.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be	SHOULD	Technology

	developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)		
100%	The industrial standard file format (landxml) for topographic data is supported.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms (arm64) must be present.	MUST	Technology
100%	Unity is used for implementation. A windows system is used.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
Privacy requirements			
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		

Table 7: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the virtual pit geometry/tool guidance system with matrix display and light feedback

3.3 Calibrated environment projection

The main part of this XR technology is a prototype, consisting of a laser-projector, a visible-light projector, and a camera. With this prototype, we can project primitives on the surroundings of vehicles. Furthermore, we use the GPS signal from the machine to localize with a known 3D terrain (e.g., in the snow groomer use-case this 3D terrain is a digital model of the mountain). Since we know our position and the mounting position of the prototype on the snow groomer, we can project the primitives for the operator in a visually correct (i.e., undistorted) way. Furthermore, our setup allows it to predefine primitives on the environmental model. Then, primitives (such as warning signs or other indicators) are projected at points of interest, whenever the vehicle drives into its proximity. The environmental model with laser primitives is visualized on a screen inside the cabin. The fulfillment of requirements that apply to this technology are stated in the table below.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	Technology
100%	Indicators on the screen inside the cabin indicate if it's operational.	Technology Assessment	D6.1/D5.1

GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	Technology
100%	They are fully integrated into the snow groomer machinery.	Technology Assessment	D6.1/D5.1
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	Technology
50%	Because it is a visualization device it is not meant to scan the environment, but rather visualize data that is scanned with other sensors (e.g., a thermal camera)	Technology Assessment	D6.1/D5.1
GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	Technology
100%	The laser-projected UI is XR-based (Spatial Augmented Reality)	Technology Assessment	D6.1/D5.1
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Technology
50%	No haptic, only visual feedback for this operator support system.	Technology Assessment	D6.1/D5.1
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception.	MUST	Technology
100%	With the switch of a button, the operator can turn of the XR-based system	Technology Assessment	D6.1/D5.1
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is on if it's not turned off by the operator.	Technology Assessment	D6.1/D5.1
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology
100%	The frame rate of the laser/projector is sufficiently fast.	Functional Testing	D5.1
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	It is fully compatible.	Functional Testing	D6.1/D6.5
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only	SHOULD	Technology

	authorized individuals or entities can access personal data		
100%	No personal data can be accessed by unauthorized personal	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology. If an image is taken to calibrate the environment via structured light, it is encrypted and deleted after the calibration process.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personally identifiable information is collected or retained.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it	MUST	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology. If an image is taken to calibrate the environment via structured light, it is encrypted and deleted after the calibration process.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
100%	We argue that all 4 areas are improved.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The system collected only environmental, non-human data		
Technical Requirements			

TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. framerate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic devices in environment projection system		
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic devices in environment projection system		
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
100%	The supply voltage is in the correct range to power our prototype.	Functional Testing	D6.5/D6.1
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	We use solely C++ and C#.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	We use the CAN interface to retrieve the GPS location information. Also, Ethernet is used to communicate internally and to external visualization devices.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	Both communication buses are present and used.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)	SHOULD	Technology

100%	We use existing environmental meshes and GPS signals (from the CAN bus) for our prototype.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms (arm64) has to be present.	MUST	Technology
100%	We obtained a Unity license for testing purposes for embedded visualizations.	Technology Assessment	TTC
Privacy requirements			
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	This technology does not detect objects (solely the visualization of potential other sensors).	Technology Assessment	D5.1
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
100%	This technology does not detect objects (solely the visualization of potential other sensors).	Technology Assessment	D5.1

Table 8: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the calibrated environment projection

3.4 LiDAR augmented 3D Data on GUI

This XR-technology uses spatial and visual data from a LiDAR sensor attached to the machine recording the environment around the machine that is affected by the machine's tools. This data is then spatially overlaid with a reference 3D model displayed on a terminal display at the operation environment. The fulfillment of requirements that apply to this technology are stated in the table below.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	Technology
100%	If the visual system is on, it is fully operational.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The LiDAR system and the 3D machine control are implemented on the excavator.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is operational during the tasks. The system is not used to scan dangerous situations.	Technology Assessment	D6.1

GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	Technology
100%	Implemented through augmenting digital 3D models with LiDAR based footage of the real environment	Technology Assessment	D6.1
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Technology
50%	The support system offers only visual feedback. Haptic features are implemented for the haptic track controls in snow grooming use-case.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system does not interfere with the direct view and can be switched off, if desired.	User Evaluation	D6.1
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is functional during the whole activity of the machine, if the operator activates it.	Functional Testing	D6.1
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is not used for safety functions.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is integrated with the electronic system of the machine (CAN-Bus)	Technology Assessment	D6.1
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data can be accessed by unauthorized personal	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally	SHOULD	Technology

	identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.		
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it	MUST	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
100%	The features increase performance as it gives an enhanced overview of the working area and the digital design model.	User Evaluation	D6.1
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No objection detection model is in place.		
Technical Requirements			
TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. framerate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic devices in LiDAR GUI		
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic devices in LiDAR GUI		
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system runs on 24VDC.	Technology Assessment	D6.1

TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The system is implemented in C#.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The Lidar is interfaced via Ethernet and the other sensors via CAN.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The Lidar is interfaced via Ethernet and the other sensors via CAN.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)	SHOULD	Technology
100%	IMU and GNSS data as well as geometry information are part of the visualization.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms (arm64) must be present.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is implemented in unity and runs on Windows.	Technology Assessment	D6.1
Privacy requirements			
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		

Table 9: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the LiDAR-augmented 3D data on GUI

3.5 Remote Operation Terminal with Augmented Camera Streams

This concept enables operators to control heavy machinery from a distance using a station equipped with multiple live video feeds enhanced by augmented reality. The system combines real-time camera views—such as cabin perspective, and top-down spreader view—with digital overlays and sensor data to improve depth perception and situational awareness. Augmented content (e.g., spatial positioning, warnings) is integrated into the streams, and visualization can occur on normal monitor or large power walls. This approach addresses challenges like limited depth perception in remote control and enhances safety and precision during operations. The fulfillment of requirements that apply to this technology are stated in the table below.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	Technology
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: The remote operation station is not on machine		
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	Technology
100%	Functional testing, 360° cameras-based object recognition	Functional testing	D6.5
GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	Technology
100%	Observation, 360° camera based AR system with two cameras	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Technology
75%	Functional testing, visual and audio feedback in real machine and haptic feedback in virtual model	Functional testing	D6.5

GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception.	MUST	Technology
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified with actual machine	End-user evaluation	D6.5
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	Technology
100%	Functional testing, 360° cameras were installed to reach stager	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: Remote operation station is not on machine		
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data	SHOULD	Technology
100%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case	MUST	Technology

	shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it		
100%	No personal data is stored by this technology.	Technology Assessment	D6.5
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	Functional testing, Exploiting already tested and verified models	Functional testing	D6.5
Technical Requirements			
TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. framerate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The haptic joystick was not integrated into the final remote operation terminal. The requirement regarding the haptic devices by themselves was fulfilled and validated through interfacing with a teleoperation simulation (see Section 4.7 and deliverables D3.4 and 4.8).	Functional testing	D6.5
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
100%	The haptic joystick was not integrated into the final remote operation terminal. The requirement regarding the haptic devices by themselves was fulfilled and validated through interfacing with a teleoperation simulation (see Section 4.7 and deliverables D3.4 and 4.8).	Functional testing	D6.5
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range	MUST	Technology

	of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.		
	Not applicable: Remote operation station is not on machine		
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	Functional testing, exploiting Unity3D	Functional testing	D6.5
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
50%	Functional testing, Implemented in KALMAR's HIL simulator	Functional testing	D3.4&D6.5
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
50%	Functional testing, Implemented in KALMAR's HIL simulator	Functional testing	D3.4&D6.5
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)	SHOULD	Technology
50%	Functional testing, Implemented in KALMAR's HIL simulator	Functional testing	D3.4&D6.5
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms (arm64) has to be present.	MUST	Technology
50%	Functional testing, Implemented Windows visualization	Functional testing	D3.4&D6.5
Privacy requirements			
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		

Table 10: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the remote operation terminal with augmented camera streams

3.6 Haptic Feedback Joystick

This technology component encompasses a pair of haptic track control levers, capable of providing independent 1 degree-of-freedom torque feedback and vibrotactile feedback in each of the levers, as well as a 6 degree-of-freedom force and torque feedback joystick featuring an interchangeable vibrotactile handle. The technology components are described in detail in deliverable D5.6 (“Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (final version)”), and the design of the haptic feedback cues for use-cases 1 and 2 (haptics were not planned in use-case 3) are described in deliverable 4.8 (“Interaction Concepts (final version)”). Experimental validation activities are reported mainly in deliverables D6.5 (“Deployment, testing and demonstration of the THEIA-XR use-cases (final version)”) for use-case 1, and D3.4 (“Low-fidelity XR prototypes (final version)”) for use-case 2. The fulfillment of requirements that apply to this technology are stated in the table below.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	Technology
100%	The haptic device controllers feature status indicator LED segment displays, provide status information over the Ethernet interface, and compensate for friction when functional, providing additional haptic cues of operational state	Functional testing	D6.5
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The haptic devices, controllers, power supplies and network interfaces were installed inside the snow groomer	Functional testing	D6.5
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: The haptic controls are not environment sensors		
GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	Technology
100%	Force and tactile feedback are XR features providing information about the vehicle and environment	Functional testing	D6.5
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Technology
100%	The haptic devices complement feedback features in other modalities	Functional testing	D6.5
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator’s perception.	MUST	Technology
100%	No negative feedback was reported in the end user studies for use cases 1 and 2.	End-user evaluation	D3.10

General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	Technology
75%	Validated in interaction with multiple tasks in simulated environments for both use-cases 1 and 2. The devices were not used in tests in the field for safety reasons.	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology
50%	Velocity-dependent feedback, in particular for collision avoidance, was implemented and successfully validated in UC1. Consideration of the speed of motion was not taken into account for UC2 haptic feedback functions.	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
75%	A versatile standard Ethernet-based communication protocol with the haptic controller was implemented and used successfully in simulation tests (see D5.3). The devices were not tested in the field with an interface to the vehicle controller.	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data can be accessed by un-authorized personal	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The haptic devices do not process or store personal data during operation.	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The haptic devices process minimal amounts of data relating exclusively to instantaneous device and vehicle state relevant to the feedback functions, which entirely excludes any personal data. No state data is recorded during operation.	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a	MUST	Technology

	privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it		
100%	See GNFR8	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
100%	All haptic features tested with end-users, be it in use-case 1 (see D6.5) or use-case 2 (see D3.4) yielded at least positive feedback regarding user experience. In the case of use-case 1, notable safety and performance improvements were achieved (see D6.5)	Functional testing	D6.5
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable to haptic devices		
Technical Requirements			
TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. framerate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The haptics ECU (UC1) and the HapticServer PC software (UC2) both guarantee control thread loop frequency >500Hz (usually approx. 1kHz). Ping tests on the wired ethernet connection between Haptics ECU or simulation PC and haptic devices systematically show latency <= 1ms. USB communication with the vibrotactile controller is set to a real-time loop with a cadence of 50Hz, with a theoretical minimum round-trip time of approx. 0.1ms (8.6µs/bit at 115200 baud, with one-byte messages, i.e. 8bits+3bit overhead). These values are well below the cadence and latency values for the visual feedback components.	Functional testing	D6.5
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
100%	Control and feedback loops are decoupled by design, allowing all haptic devices to function as pure input	Functional testing	D6.5

	controllers. This was validated in principle for the primary haptic joystick for UC2 (substituted with a Haption Virtuose 6D arm following the same software design principles – see D3.4), and in practice for the track controls in UC1 interfaces with the Creanex Simulator (see D4.8 and D6.5).		
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
100%	A modular power supply was designed for the haptic devices, accepting both 220VAC and 24VDC power supply, depending on whether it is interfaced with a simulator or vehicle (see D5.6).	Functional testing	D6.5
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The haptic feedback functions are developed in C++ for use-case 1 (entirely hosted on the haptics ECU), and in C++ and C# for use-case 2 (HapticService software in C++, Unity components in C#)	Functional testing	D6.5
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The haptics controller (Haptics ECU) interfaces with the other system components over Ethernet.	Functional testing	D6.5
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The haptics controller (Haptics ECU) interfaces with the other system components over Ethernet.	Functional testing	D6.5
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable to haptic devices		
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded linux platforms (arm64) has to be present.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable to haptic devices		
Privacy requirements			
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology

	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No object detection model is used.		

Table 11: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the haptic feedback joystick

3.7 Thermal Camera with Object Recognition

This technology consists of one or more thermal cameras which perform object detection within the thermal domain, i.e., on the received infrared images. This technology comes to play with our “Panotherm” prototype, which is a panoramic thermal camera, with which a 360° thermal view can be received and processed. The thermal images can be visualized in the cabin via embedded visualization. Besides panoramic thermal imagery, object detection on the thermal cameras is also deployed with rugged thermal cameras and a connected display, visualizing thermal imagery and objects within it. Note that this technology can be paired with other visualization techniques, i.e., the laser-projector prototype (see Section 3.3). The fulfillment of requirements that apply to this technology are stated in the table below.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	Technology
100%	If they are turned on, they are fully operational.	Test Method	D5.1
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	Technology
100%	They are integrated in the cabin as display AR or with the laser/projector prototype.	Functional Testing	D6.5/D5.1/D5.2
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	Technology
100%	Whenever the system is operational, the images are processed, and potential objects are detected.	Technology Assessment	D6.5/D5.1
GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	Technology
100%	The detection results can be either displayed inside the cabin or visualized with the laser projector.	Technology Assessment	D6.5/D5.1

GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Technology
50%	Only visual (no haptic feedback) is supported	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception.	MUST	Technology
100%	The system can be turned off if the operator finds it distracting.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is functional when it is turned on.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	Technology
100%	Inference speed of object detection methods are within 0.1 seconds.	Functional Testing	D5.1
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The system is compatible with the embedded system inside the machinery.	Functional Testing	D6.5
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored. Thermal images are processed on the device, i.e., after inference, the images are disregarded and not saved.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR7	Personal data collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored. Thermal images are processed on the device, i.e., after inference, the images are disregarded and not saved.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimization, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	Technology

100%	No personal data is stored. Thermal images are processed on the device, i.e., after inference, the images are disregarded and not saved.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it	MUST	Technology
100%	No personal data is stored. Thermal images are processed on the device, i.e., after inference, the images are disregarded and not saved.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Technology
100%	The situational awareness is enhanced with this technology.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	Since we use thermal images, the fairness of the object detector is given.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
Technical Requirements			
TR1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. frame-rate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic devices in thermal camera		
TR2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure, and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable: No haptic devices in thermal camera		

TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	Technology
100%	The technology works within the voltage provided by the prototypes.	Functional Testing	D6.5
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	We programming language in use is C++.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	The sensors have Ethernet to communicate with the other devices.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	Technology
100%	The sensors have Ethernet to communicate with the other devices.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)	SHOULD	Technology
	Not applicable		
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms (arm64) has to be present.	MUST	Technology
	Not applicable		
Privacy requirements			
PR5	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Technology
100%	Since we use thermal images, the fairness of the object detector is given.	Technology Assessment	D5.1
PR6	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	Technology
100%	Whenever we use object detection, a sticker shall inform about it.	Technology Assessment	D5.1

Table 12: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the thermal camera with object recognition

3.8 Use Case 1 – Snow Grooming

The focus is on Prinoth's snow groomer for alpine slope preparation. Operators currently rely on cabin-based machine operation using non-augmented hardware controls, direct sight and terminal displays for accessing digital data and 3D models. The applied solutions introduce advanced obstacle awareness, navigation, and tool movements through XR based light and haptic feedback and environment projections.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements			
FR.UC1.001	The XR HMI system must show the distance between actual and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Projected height distance indicator implemented and tested in simulation	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC1.002	The XR HMI system must show the distance between the blade and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	Use Case
90%	Functional testing in simulation (demonstrator cabin) with indicator bar; not implemented in real machine. Matrix LED can be used for real machine implementation.	Evaluation	D6.5
FR.UC1.003	The XR HMI system must show the distance between tracks and target height in an intuitive way.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Projected height distance indicator implemented and tested in simulation	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC1.004	The XR HMI system should indicate the required action to minimize delta to target surface	SHOULD	Use Case
90%	Functional testing in simulation (demonstrator cabin) with indicator bar; not implemented in real machine, implementation could be done by using Matrix LED	Evaluation	D6.5
FR.UC1.005	The XR HMI system should inform operator on fulfilment rate	SHOULD	Use Case
40%	Functional testing in simulation (demonstrator cabin) with fulfilment summary at end of path following; not implemented in real machine	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC1.006	The XR HMI system must inform operators in case of obstacle or boundary proximity.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Functional testing in simulation (demonstrator cabin) with LEDs around, windscreen, around display and with haptic feedback in track controls	Functional testing & Evaluation	D6.4 D6.5
FR.UC1.007	The XR HMI system must inform operator in case of new static or dynamic obstacle information availability	MUST	Use Case

100%	Light feedback function is implemented to inform the operator about obstacles in real time	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC1.008	The XR HMI system must inform operator about location and identification of obstacle	MUST	Use Case
100%	Functional testing in simulation (demonstrator cabin) with LEDs around, windscreen, around display and with haptic feedback in track controls	Functional testing & Evaluation	D6.4 D6.5
FR.UC1.009	The XR HMI system must inform operator about proposed action to avoid collision with an obstacle	MUST	Use Case
100%	Functional testing in simulation (demonstrator cabin) with haptic force feedback in track controls	Functional testing & Evaluation	D6.4 D6.5
Technical Requirements			
TR7	Physical means will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to mount external equipment (e.g., rooftop mount for projectors, active lights and cameras)	MUST	Use Case
100%	Assembly positions and supports have been provided in real snow groomer and in demonstrator cabin	Functional Testing	D6.1; D6.4
TR8	Electrical powering facilities and wiring options will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to power external equipment (e.g., up to 220V power rails for active lights and projectors)	MUST	Use Case
100%	All required wiring is provided in real snow groomer and in Demonstrator cabin	Functional Testing	D6.1; D6.4
Privacy Requirements			
PR1	The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing	MUST	Use Case
100%	Personal data checklist completed	Evaluation	D7.6
PR2	The use cases shall adopt a data minimization approach	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	See sections 3.1 to 3.7	Functional testing	D6.5
PR3	When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	Regular consultation of privacy experts within the consortium was realized	Functional testing	D7.6
PR4	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	See sections 3.1 to 3.7	Functional testing	D6.5

Table 13: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to use case 1 – snow grooming

3.9 Use Case 2 - Logistics

The focus is on UC2/KALMAR's remote-controlled reachstacker for container handling in harbors. Operators currently rely on video screens, which makes depth perception and awareness of hidden objects difficult. The solution introduces XR-based remote operation of AR-enhanced 360° camera views combined with sensor data.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements			
FR.UC2.001	The teleoperation support system should show the operator the job order via AR/XR in video feed. E.g., also highlights container location	SHOULD	Use Case
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
FR.UC2.002	The teleoperation support system must show to operator spreader corner in video overlay via AR/XR	MUST	Use Case
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
FR.UC2.003	The teleoperation support system should show to operator distance between handled objects (e.g., spreader and container) in video overlay via AR/XR	SHOULD	Use Case
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
FR.UC2.004	The teleoperation support system must allow to operator to choose XR supported 3D and/or bird view to lift/lay down container without collision	MUST	Use Case
100%	Multiple camera streams and switching function implemented	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC2.005	The teleoperation support system should provide to operator XR-supported safety warning, if someone (human or machine is arriving close to working area	SHOULD	Use Case
25%	Observation, partly implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
FR.UC2.006	The teleoperation support system must provide haptic feedback to operator	MUST	Use Case
100%	Observation, Implemented to actual reach stager remote operation station	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
FR.UC2.007	The teleoperation support system must provide audio feedback to operator from distance and location before collision	MUST	Use Case
50%	Observation, Implemented and verified in Virtual model in XR lab	End-user evaluation	D3.4&D6.5
Technical Requirements			
TR7	Physical means will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to mount external equipment (e.g., rooftop mount for projectors, active lights and cameras)	MUST	Use Case

100%	Functional testing, 360° cameras were installed to reach stager	Functional testing	D6.5
TR8	Electrical powering facilities and wiring options will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to power external equipment (e.g., up to 220V power rails for active lights and projectors)	MUST	Use Case
100%	Functional testing, reachstacker had all required wiring for 360° cameras and communications	Functional testing	D6.5
Privacy Requirements			
PR1	The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing	MUST	Use Case
100%	Personal data checklist completed	Evaluation	D7.6
PR2	The use cases shall adopt a data minimization approach	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	See sections 3.1 to 3.7	Functional testing	D6.5
PR3	When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	Regular consultation of privacy experts within the consortium was realized	Functional testing	D7.6
PR4	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	See sections 3.1 to 3.7	Functional testing	D6.5

Table 14: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to use case 2 - logistics

3.10 Use Case 3 - Construction

The focus is on excavators for construction tasks. Operators currently rely on cabin-based machine operation using non-augmented hardware controls, direct sight and terminal displays for accessing digital data and 3D models. The applied solutions introduce advanced obstacle awareness, navigation, and tool movements through XR based light and haptic feedback and environmental projections.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements			
FR.UC3.001	The operator interface system must visualize a digital representation of the machine and a terrain model of the environment.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Implemented in the terminal GUI	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC3.002	The operator interface system must visualize the excavator’s bucket position in relation to the target design height at that particular position	MUST	Use Case
100%	Implemented in the terminal GUI and the matrix display	Functional testing	D6.5

FR.UC3.004	The operator interface system must visualize the point cloud data from the LiDAR as a continuously updated map.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Implemented in the terminal GUI	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC2.005	The operator interface system must inform the operator about persons in the slewing radius in an intuitive but unobtrusive way.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Implemented as light feedback function	User testing	D6.5&D3.10
FR.UC3.006	The operator interface system should augment video streams with digital design data.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	Video streams of surround cameras visible in terminal GUI and augmented with spatial distance markers	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC3.007	The operator interface system should visualize the overall working area and the delta between actual and target height across the whole map.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	Implemented as LiDAR-fed height map in 3D model view on terminal GUI	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC3.008	The operator interface system should show the position of known underground media in an intuitive way.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	Implemented in the terminal GUI	Functional testing	D6.5
FR.UC3.009	The operator interface system should enable the operator to modify the digital design model within the augmented video feed.	SHOULD	Use Case
0%	Not implemented		
Use Case Specific Non-Functional Requirements			
UCNFR.2 (UC3)	The displayed information and visualization must represent the actual situation with a maximal latency of 1s or clearly indicate an insufficient visualization.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Latency under 1s assured	Functional testing	D6.5
UCNFR.3 (UC3)	Any sensor or system function which is not operable must be clearly shown on the UI so that the operator can assess the system's functionality.	MUST	Use Case
100%	Implemented in the terminal GUI	Functional testing	D6.5
UCNFR.4 (UC3)	The system must be operable even if no sufficient GNSS signal is available.	MUST	Use Case
100%	System is operable also without GNSS	Functional testing	D6.5
Technical Requirements			

TR7	Physical means will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to mount external equipment (e.g., rooftop mount for projectors, active lights and cameras)	MUST	Use Case
100%	Fully functional excavator was available throughout the whole project	Functional testing	D6.5
TR8	Electrical powering facilities and wiring options will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to power external equipment (e.g., up to 220V power rails for active lights and projectors)	MUST	Use Case
100%	Power supply implemented	Functional testing	D6.5
Privacy Requirements			
PR1	The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing	MUST	Use Case
100%	Personal data checklist completed	Evaluation	D7.6
PR2	The use cases shall adopt a data minimization approach	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	See sections 3.1 to 3.7	Functional testing	D6.5
PR3	When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	Regular consultation of privacy experts within the consortium was realized	Functional testing	D7.6
PR4	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	SHOULD	Use Case
100%	See sections 3.1 to 3.7	Functional testing	D6.5

Table 15: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to use case 3 - construction

3.11 Universal XR HMI

The general XR user interface concept consists of several output components and defines how this output is used to present information and how operators can manipulate XR functions.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Functional Requirements			
GFR6	The operator support system should allow users to customize UI components	SHOULD	UI Concept
100%	The general XR-interaction concept defines a set of adjustable characteristics (adaptive XR dimensions; level of detail, level of virtuality, visualization mode, information presentation location) that operators should be able to change	Lab-based testing with functional prototype	D4.8

	to adapt the XR system to personal preferences or situational requirements. Means of manipulation options (haptic control panel, gestures) have been realized and tested in the interaction Lab (TUD)		
GFR7	The operator must be able to overcome the guidance provided by the support system, as he/she is the ultimate decision-maker.	MUST	UI Concept
100%	Our XR-technologies do not interfere with the machine controls and only provide visual and haptic guidance that can be ignored or disabled at any time.	Lab tested	D3.10
GFR8	A software development toolkit must be available for developing UIs and hosting XR applications on the visualization infrastructure and interaction systems.	SHOULD	UI Concept
20%	A universal toolkit is not available as the proprietary machine-based solutions differ significantly. However, the code of the developed software is available for third-party companies based on licensing.	Dissemination	D7.4
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR11	The design of the overall system architecture should have the potential to be extended to support new/additional sensors, XR technologies, or output devices.	SHOULD	UI Concept
100%	The developed systems work on a sensor-input, data processing and output device architecture that allows for implementing additional sensors and alternate output devices to apply its functional logics.	Lab tested	D3.10
GNFR13	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	SHOULD	UI Concept
100%	The general XR-interaction concept considers this requirement with a customization component where operators can disable sensors (while being informed about the functional consequences) or delete stored data (if any exists).	Lab-based testing with functional prototype	D4.8
GNFR15	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing the use of this system.	MUST	UI Concept
100%	A sticker template has been designed, that machine manufacturers can use to inform users about the sensing and data storing functions of the machine.	Lab-based testing with functional prototype	D4.8
Privacy requirements			

PR7	Where UX-enhanced features are integrated into the system interface, there should be a clear method for users to opt in or opt out.	SHOULD	UI Concept
100%	The general XR-interaction concept considers this requirement with a customization component where operators can disable UX-features (while being informed about the functional consequences).	Lab-based testing with functional prototype	D4.8

Table 16: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the universal XR user interface

3.12 Development procedure

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Reference
General Non-Functional Requirements			
GNFR4	The design and development process must involve representative vehicle operators in all major design and evaluation activities and provide them with opportunities to influence design and development decisions for their respective use-case.	MUST	Dev Process
85%	Recruitment efforts, attendance lists, and documented feedback confirm continuous operator involvement in design and validation. End-user involvement was high in use case 1 with access to operators provided by PRIN, highest in use case 3 with access to operators (construction vehicle trainers and trainees) provided by external education partners, and lowest in use case 2 with access to operators provided by only one external partner, despite multiple attempts to gain more participants from other sources. Female participation remained limited, also despite multiple attempts to contact this target group. All participating operators were enabled and encouraged to work directly with scenarios and concepts, with their input integrated into subsequent iterations and co-design phases.	Process documents, participant database	D3.6, D3.7
GNFR5	During the design and implementation of feature ideas and interaction concepts, the utility, usability, safety and positive user experience for the human operators should always be prioritized above conflicting interests, unless technical feasibility is not given, or privacy infringements are detected.	SHOULD	Dev Process
75%	Within the co-design process, user feedback led to certain functional developments being prioritized or discarded, based on perceived usefulness, usability, safety concerns, and contribution to wellbeing and	Process documents	D3.7

	positive user experience. However, due to co-design and technical development running in parallel, it was not possible to steer the development process entirely based on user feedback. For this, the ideation and vision scenario phase would need to be completed even before the start of relevant development and engineering work.		
GNFR10	At least one concept for positive user experience must be integrated and tested in one of the final demonstrators.	MUST	Dev Process
50%	The implemented and tested concepts and technologies related to collision avoidance in all use cases can be considered to address the need for safety and evoke the feelings of relief and predictability. However, none of the other concepts explicitly designed to address psychological needs, e.g., self-efficacy, meaningfulness or relatedness, have been implemented or tested. This unfortunately must be attributed to most partners' effort and time budget for additional developments having run out by the time the UX concepts were completed and validated.	Process documents	D3.7

Table 17: Fulfilment of requirements that apply to the development procedure

4 Conclusions

Throughout all use cases, lab and machine-based prototypes were built to explore effective means of XR technologies in machine operation. These prototypes were used for technical and functional testing regarding identified requirements and KPIs. Technical tests, expert workshops, and user studies provided feedback that was used to rate requirement fulfilment levels. As a result, a high fulfilment level for THEIA^{XR} can be concluded. Applying the **79** defined requirements to the developed XR technologies, use cases, components and procedures resulted in **230** tested requirement items, of which **136** were defined as MUST, and **94** as SHOULD.

Out of these 230 items **164** were fulfilled to 100%, **5** achieved high ratings between 100 and 80%. **31** achieved intermediate ratings between 97 and 20%, of which **19** concern requirements labeled as MUST. **2** Requirement items were rated with a 0% fulfilment-rate. The remaining **30** items did not apply to the respective technology, use case, component, or procedure.

Regarding the **136** MUST items, the following ratio of fulfilment levels can be reported: Full (100%): 98, High (80-99%): 4, Partly (19), Not at all (0%): 0, where 15 did not apply.

Regarding the **94** MUST items, the following ratio of fulfilment levels can be reported: Full (100%): 68, High (80-99%): 2, Partly (9), Not at all (0%): 2, where 13 did not apply.

Figure 1: Ratio of fulfilment levels for SHOULD, MUST and overall requirement items

The **19** only partly fulfilled MUST requirements comprise:

- The implementation of multimodal UI elements (5x, ratings: 50%, 75%), which were rated below 80% because the single technologies often address only one modality. However, the overall XR system is multimodal.
- The testing of fairness of implemented object detection models (rating: 66%) was not feasible. However, the use of thermal cameras was proposed.
- The implementation of feedback functions that clearly indicate if the XR technology is fully operational or not (50% must) was not applied for all implemented functions.
- The verification of the potential to distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception (UC2, 50%) could not sufficiently be ruled out as the system was not fully integrated in the final machine.
- The enhancement of HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience (UC2, 50%) could not completely verified due to the limited number of operators participating in the evaluation study.
- The support of support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) (UC2)
- The availability of a Unity license for embedded Linux platforms which was not necessary at some point.
- The guaranteed functionality during the whole activity of the machine, as the use cases focused on three representative tasks.
- To inform the human operator about a dangerous situation depending on the speed of motion (75%), which was not tested for the haptic feedback function.
- To ensure compatibility with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery, which was not tested for the haptic feedback function in UC2.
- To provide audio feedback to operator from distance and location before collision (50%, UC2), which was not implemented fully functional.
- To integration and test concepts for positive user experience that shifted out of focus as usability, functionality, and privacy-related criteria have taken precedence even if positive user experience UI concepts have been developed.

The **2** not fulfilled SHOULD requirements comprise:

- To use C, C++ or C# as software language for function implementation (3.1, Should), but Python was used instead.
- To implement a function that enables the operator to modify the digital design model (UC3, Should), which was not realized in the final demonstrator.

In all three use cases, the utilization of XR environments combined with human-centric evaluation and design methodologies has proven to be a powerful approach for improved operation performance. In fulfilling most of the defined requirements we ensured that these technologies not only meet the requirements of operators but also are in line with European standards regarding privacy and the aim to be applicable in industry and future solutions, manifesting substantial impact.

ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

[3D]	Three-dimensional
[AR]	Augmented Reality
[CAN]	Controller Area Network
[D]	Deliverable
[GDPR]	General Data Protection Regulation
[GNSS]	Global Navigation Satellite System
[GPS]	Global Positioning System
[GUI]	Graphical User Interface
[HIL]	Hardware-in-the-Loop
[HMI]	Human-machine Interface
[KPI]	Key Performance Indicator
[LED]	Light-emitting Diode, or in general a light source based on this technology
[LiDAR]	Light Detection and Ranging
[UC]	Use case
[UI]	User Interface
[UX]	User Experience
[WP]	Work package
[XR]	Extended Reality